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Research Article

Formulation, Development and Evaluation of Lip Serum

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ABSTRACT

Lip dehydration and cracking are undesired side effects of photo degradation and ultraviolet (UV) rays. There are currently no viable ways for delaying the lip-damaging process. Other synthetic items are high-concentration cosmetic products. When we use honey, coconut oil, and almond oil, we get not only instant cosmetic effects but also psychological satisfactions. Serum has the virtue of rapid absorption and ability to enter into the skin. Honey is a natural humectant, has emollient properties, and retains moisture, keeping your lips moistened all day. Coconut oil has soothing characteristics and absorbs fast, restoring moisture to dry and chapped lips. Almond oil includes vitamins A, E, and K, which protect your lips from UV rays and brighten them. Rose oil contains anti-inflammatory properties and enhances pigmentation while moisturizing the lips. Massage with lip serum helps to lighten dark lips. The lip serum was tested for physiochemical criteria such as pH, globule size, and consistency. The stability research results revealed that there was no change in visual appearance, homogeneity, or globule size.

INTRODUCTION

A lip serum is a lightweight, oil- or water-based solution designed to help prevent trans-epidermal water loss while also strengthening the lips' thin skin. It can comprise nourishing oils as well as active and moisturizing substances including antioxidants, humectants, hyaluronic acid, and vitamins. The lip serum moisturizes the skin considerably. Lips appear vibrant, moisturized, toned, and healthy[1]. With active booster, the

skin's natural biological function is stimulated, resulting in increased protein, collagen, and DNA production while also protecting the cell from free radicals. Lip serum is formulated with natural oils and other useful elements to nourish and moisten the lips. They have a consistency that falls in between lip gloss and lip balm. Lip serum is made out of oils derived from substances including almond and coconut, as well as honey[1]. These natural ingredients are rich in fatty acids, vitamins,

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and antioxidants, all of which are extremely nutritious and moisturizing.

Ideal Characteristics of Lip Serum:

- Best hydrating and conditioning property
- Best long-lasting effect.
- Best anti-aging property.
- Best glossy effect.
- Best quick-absorbing capacity.

Anatomy of Lips:

The lips function as organs of prehension, suction, and speech. It consists of skin, superficial fascia, orbicularis muscle, and surrounding muscles (areolar tissue and mucous membrane) [1]. The lips' borders are coated with a dry, crimson mucous membrane that is continuous with the skin and contains many vascular papillae and touch corpuscles. The mucosal membrane is internally reflected from the top and lower lips onto the gums, forming two superioris and inferioris folds along the median line[3].

Fig No: - 1

Formulation Tabel: -

Sr. No.	Ingredient Name	Use	F1	F2	F3
1	Rose oil	Anti-inflammatory	1.5 ml	1 ml	1.5 ml
2	Raspberry syrup	Smoothing Agent	2.5ml	3ml	3.5ml
3	Glycerin	Thickening Agent	2 ml	2.5 ml	2.5 ml
4	Almond oil	Vit A, E, K	1 ml	1 ml	1 ml
5	Coconut oil	Moisturizer	1 ml	0.5 ml	1 ml
6	Saffron	Lightning Agent	1 gm	1 gm	0.5 gm
7	Honey	Humectant	1 ml	1 ml	1 ml
8	Vit. E		-	-	-

Equipment:

Fig:-2 Emulsifier

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The medical store purchased almond oil, vitamin E capsules, coconut oil, honey, and glycerin. Saffron rose oil and raspberry syrup were obtained online.

Methods Of Preparation:

1. Preparation

Sterilize your utensils and working area, and wear proper lab PPE in accordance with GMP.

2. Weighing

Weigh the oils individually into a glass beaker, as stated. If you are concerned about precisely weighing them in the same beaker, separate them first.

3. Blending

Mix the oil mixture gently with a glass rod or a stainless steel implement, such as a spatula or long-handled spoon, until it is homogeneous.

4. Bottling

Pour the combination into your preferred dropper bottle and label it with the date of manufacture.

Evolution Test:

1. Appearance:

Batch	F1	F2	F3
Appearance	Liquid	Liquid	Liquid

Colour:

Batch	F1	F2	F3
Colour	Light Pink	Light Pink	Light Pink

3. Odour:

Batch	F1	F2	F3
Odour	Rose Aroma	Rose Aroma	Rose Aroma

4. pH: pH meter is used to calculate pH.

Batch	F1	F2	F3
pH			

5. Spreadability Test: Spreadability calculated by using glass slide.

Batch	F1	F2	F3
Spreadability Test	26.72 Sec	26.69 Sec	26.71 Sec

F1

F2

F3

Fig 3:-Spreadability Test

6. Viscosity: We used Brookfield viscometer to check viscosity.

Batch	F1	F2	F3
Viscosity	61.8	61.9	63.5

Fig F1

Fig F2

Fig F3

Fig 4: -Viscosity Test

RESULT:

When we perform the evolution test for lip serum the F1 batch is better than other two batches i.e. F2 and F3. In the appearance test the all F1, F2.F3 is in liquid form and colors are Light Pink of F1, F2, F3 batches. The odor tests of all batches are same

it is rose aroma, the viscosity for f1 batch is 61.8 is better than F2 batch is 61.9 and F3 batch is 63.5. The Spreadability test of F1 batch is greater than F2and F3 batch. Ph of F1 batch is 5.6 is better than F2 5.4 and F3 5.5. In all result of batches the batch F1 is better than other batches. Final result is batch F1 is good for lip.

Fig:-5

Fig:-6

CONCLUSION:

When creating new products, cosmetic chemists select from thousands of chemicals, but they always make sure to choose ones with chemical features that improve the product's look, feel, and use. For example, no one wants lip serum to be overly harsh, thus most homemade lip serum recipes include some form of oil. Oils are thick, viscous liquids at room temperature that are emollients, which means they soften and smooth the skin.

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